

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

NON-DESTRUCTIVE ABSORPTION OF A SMALL COUNTER-ROTATING VORTEX BY A SPHERICAL HILL VORTEX

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Abstract

Within the framework of an ideal incompressible fluid, the problem of absorption of a small counter-rotating vortex by a spherical Hill vortex in a non-destructive regime ($\varepsilon \ll 1$) is considered. Unlike the work of Moffatt and Moore [2], which investigated axisymmetric perturbations of the same sign, the present study addresses the physically significant case of capturing a counter-rotating vortex. A Gaussian model of a localized vortical perturbation is constructed; closed-form expressions are obtained for the velocity field, the vorticity perturbation $\delta\omega_\varphi$ and the asymmetry of the pressure field after the interaction. An absorption criterion is formulated in terms of the stream function. It is shown that the captured vortex does not persist as an independent structure but is redistributed along closed streamlines. Analytical expressions are derived and compared with numerical results for the changes in circulation Γ , hydrodynamic impulse I , propagation velocity U , angular momentum L_z and moment of inertia J_z . It is established that: (i) the spherical shape of the Hill vortex is preserved up to order $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$; (ii) a localized vortical core forms in the outer layers as a result of the interaction; (iii) the propagation velocity decreases by an amount proportional to I_s/I_H ; (iv) passive scalar transport is reorganized along the potential layers of the modified vortex.

Keywords: Hill vortex, vortex absorption, vorticity, stream function, vortex interaction, circulation, hydrodynamic impulse, angular momentum, axisymmetric flow, passive scalar transport, formation of a vortical core

1. Introduction. The spherical Hill vortex [1] is one of the few exact three-dimensional solutions of the Euler equations for an incompressible inviscid fluid. It propagates rectilinearly with velocity U in a quiescent medium while remaining topologically closed: all fluid inside the sphere $r^2 + z^2 < a^2$ moves along closed toroidal streamlines, whereas the external flow is potential. The combination of compactness and exact analytical structure makes this vortex a canonical object for studying transport in vortical flows [2–9].

The linear stability of the Hill vortex to small axisymmetric perturbations was studied by Moffatt and Moore [2], who showed that such perturbations preserve the vortex topology. Vortex rings—closely related structures—were examined in detail by Meleshko et al. [3], and their stretching and folding dynamics form the basis of fast dynamo theory [4, 5]. However, the question of what occurs during the capture of a counter-rotating vortex with opposite-signed impulse has not yet received a direct analytical treatment.

This scenario is physically relevant in several contexts: (a) the interaction of coherent vortical structures in turbulent flows, where vortices of opposite sign arise as a result of reconnection; (b) the capture of background vorticity by large-scale vortices; (c) magneto-hydrodynamic (MHD) dynamo models in conducting media [6], where the background vortical field modulates a translating spherical vortex. The present work fills this gap by constructing an explicit perturbation model for the absorption process and deriving closed-

form analytical expressions for all integral characteristics of the Hill vortex after absorbing a small counter-rotating vortex.

Unlike [2], where axisymmetric perturbations of the same sign were considered, the present work: (i) introduces a counter-rotating Gaussian vortex as an admixture; (ii) derives the full set of post-absorption invariants - including the angular momentum L_z , which is identically zero in the classical Hill vortex - in closed form; (iii) proves that, as a result of the interaction of the outer layers, a localized vortical core emerges ($\delta\omega_\varphi \neq Ar$) - an effect absent in all previous analytical studies; (iv) shows that passive scalar transport is reorganized along the closed potential layers of the perturbed vortex, with the impurity cloud retaining a spiral structure over timescale $\tau \sim a/U$.

2. Governing Equations of the Base Hill Vortex. We work in cylindrical coordinates (r, θ, z) , $r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$. The Hill vortex is an axisymmetric solution of the Euler equations without azimuthal velocity ($u_\theta = 0$). The stream function inside the sphere has the form:

$$\psi_H = Ar^2(a^2 - r^2 - z^2)/10 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where } A = 15u/2a^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{The vorticity region is bounded by the sphere } r^2 + z^2 < a^2. \quad (3)$$

The only nonzero component of vorticity is the azimuthal one:

$$\omega_\varphi^{(H)} = Ar = 15Ur/(2a^2), \quad (4)$$

This *linear* profile - where the vorticity increases monotonically from zero on the axis to a maximum at the equator - fundamentally distinguishes the Hill

vortex from Rankine or Lamb - Oseen vortices, which possess a compact, highly vortical core. The Hill vortex does not have a core in the classical sense: the vorticity fills the entire sphere uniformly (Fig. 1). Outside the sphere, the flow is potential:

$$\Psi_H = (Ur^2/2) \left(1 - (a^3/(r^2 + z^2)^{3/2})\right) \quad (5)$$

Velocity components inside the sphere:

$$\begin{aligned} u_r^{(H)} &= 3Urz/2a^2, \\ u_z^{(H)} &= (3U/2)(1 - ((2r^2 + z^2)/a^2)) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Hydrodynamic impulse, which determines the propagation velocity (Section 4):

$$I_H = 2\pi\rho Ua^3, \quad U = I_H/(2\pi\rho a^3) \quad (7)$$

3. Model of the captured small vortex. The incoming small vortex has radius $b = a/2$ and moves toward the Hill vortex. Its influence is introduced as a localized perturbation of the stream function:

$$\delta\psi(r, z, t) = \varepsilon Uar^2 \exp(-q/2\sigma^2) \exp(-t/\tau) \quad (8)$$

where $\varepsilon \ll 1$ is the perturbation amplitude, σ is the characteristic scale of the capture region, $\tau \sim a/U$ is the

absorption timescale, and $q = (r - r_c)^2 + (z - z_c)^2$ is the squared distance from the vortex center (r_c, z_c) . The exponential temporal decay describes the redistribution of the captured vortex along closed streamlines. The corresponding velocity perturbations are:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta u_r &= (\varepsilon Uar(z - z_c)/\sigma^2) \exp(-q/2\sigma^2), \\ \delta u_z &= \varepsilon Ua[2 - (r(r - r_c)/\sigma^2)] \exp(-q/2\sigma^2). \end{aligned} \quad (9, 10)$$

The total velocity field $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}^{(H)} + \delta\mathbf{u}$ satisfies the solenoidal condition $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$, since $\delta\psi$ is a properly defined stream function. *Absorption criterion* (the vortex center must lie on a closed streamline):

$$r_c^2 + z_c^2 < a^2 \text{ и } \psi_H(r_c, z_c) > 0 \quad (11)$$

The first condition is geometric (the center must lie inside the sphere), while the second ensures that the center lies on a *closed* streamline of ψ_H . If $\psi_H \leq 0$, the impurity will leave the vortex through the equatorial region. The non-destructive regime is ensured by the conditions $\varepsilon \ll 1$ and $\max|\delta\mathbf{u}| \ll U$.

Fig. 1. Left: streamlines of the spherical Hill vortex in the (y, z) plane (dashed circle: boundary of the sphere $r^2 + z^2 = a^2$; arrow: direction of U). Right: azimuthal vorticity $\omega_\varphi/(U/a)$ inside the sphere, confirming the linear profile $\omega_\varphi = Ar$.

4. Propagation Velocity After Absorption. We use the hydrodynamic impulse to analyze the change in propagation velocity. For an axisymmetric vortex with vorticity ω_φ :

$$I = \pi\rho \iint_D \omega_\varphi r^2 dr dz. \quad (12)$$

For the Hill vortex, this yields:

$$I_H = \pi\rho A \iint_D r^3 dr dz = 2\pi\rho Ua^3, \quad (13)$$

from which it follows that

$$U = I_H/2\pi\rho a^3 \quad (14)$$

After the absorption of a small vortex with its own impulse $I_s < 0$ (moving oppositely), into a new Hill-type structure with radius $a_+ \approx a$:

$$U_+ = (I_H + I_s)/(2\pi\rho a_+^3) \quad (15)$$

In physical terms, the deceleration of the vortex is explained by the fact that the counter-rotating vortex carries negative axial impulse, partially compensating the impulse of the Hill vortex. This represents a hydrodynamic analogue of momentum conservation. In the weak absorption regime, $|I_s| \ll I_H$ (i.e. $\varepsilon \ll 1$):

$$(U_+ - U)/U \approx I_s/I_H \sim \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon). \quad (16)$$

This confirms the non-destructive nature of the absorption: the vortex structure is preserved at leading order, while the change in velocity constitutes a small first-order correction in ε .

5. Change in Azimuthal Vorticity and Core Formation. The vorticity perturbation induced by the captured vortex is calculated as

$$\delta\omega_\varphi = (\partial\delta u_r/\partial z) - (\partial\delta u_z/\partial r) \text{ that we have:}$$

$$\delta\omega_\varphi(r, z) = -(\varepsilon Ua/\sigma^4)[r(q - 5\sigma^2) + 3r_c\sigma^2] \exp(-q/2\sigma^2). \quad (17)$$

The vorticity profile after absorption is given by:

$$\omega_\varphi^\dagger = Ar + \delta\omega_\varphi.$$

The key physical point is that $\delta\omega_\varphi$ is *not proportional to r* : the Gaussian factor introduces a localized deviation from the classical linear profile in the vicinity of (r_c, z_c) . This corresponds to the emergence of a **local vortical core** - a region of enhanced vorticity that breaks the coreless nature of the original Hill vortex. The core width is $\sim \sigma$, and its peak amplitude is $\sim \varepsilon Ua/\sigma^2 \gg Ar_c$ for $\sigma \ll r_c$. This mechanism - core formation through the interaction of outer layers - has no analogue in the theory of axisymmetric perturbations [10].

6. Circulation. The meridional circulation of the Hill vortex is described via the cross-section D :

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_H &= \iint_D \omega_\varphi^{(H)} dr dz = A \iint_D r dr dz = \\ &= 2Aa^3/3 = 5Ua \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

After absorption, the *meridional circulation* of the Hill vortex through the cross-section D is given by:

$$\Gamma_+ = \Gamma_H + \delta\Gamma, \delta\Gamma = \iint_D \delta\omega_\phi drdz. \quad (19)$$

Sign of $\delta\Gamma$. For a counter-rotating captured vortex, the perturbation $\delta\omega_\phi$ is, on average, negative over the domain D (the negative contribution in equation (16) dominates for $q \gg 5\sigma^2$), therefore, $\delta\Gamma < 0$ and the total circulation decreases. For a co-rotating vortex $\delta\Gamma > 0$. The magnitude $|\delta\Gamma| \sim \varepsilon U a \sigma = \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ relative to $\Gamma_H = 5Ua$, which is consistent with the assumption of a non-destructive regime.

7. Mass, Volume, and Density. The Hill vortex is not a rigid body; one can speak only of the mass contained within the vortical region. For an incompressible fluid of constant density ρ and an almost unchanged radius, $a_+ \approx a$:

$$V_H = 4\pi a^3/3, M_H = \rho V_H, \rho_+ = \rho. \quad (20)$$

The density remains unchanged - only the velocity field, pressure field, and vorticity distribution are modified. If the absorption is accompanied by a small expansion $\delta a \sim \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon a)$, the volume changes as $a_+^3 = a^3(1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon))$ so the correction is negligibly small at first order in ε (see Figs. 2 and 3).

Fig. 2. Pressure isocontours $P^* = -u^2/2$ in the (y, z) plane ($a = 1, U = 1, \varepsilon = 0.18$). Left: the initial spherical Hill vortex (symmetric pattern). Right: after the capture of a counter-rotating vortex at $(r_c, z_c) = (0.35, 0.25)$ with $\sigma = 0.22$. The white cross marks the center of the captured vortex. The breakdown of pressure symmetry is a direct consequence of $\delta\omega_\phi \neq 0$.

Fig. 3. (a) - (b): streamlines and isobars; the angle between them; (a) Streamlines (blue) and isobars (red); the angle between an isobar and a streamline: 0° - parallel, 90° - perpendicular. From panel (b), it is evident that inside the vortex the angle is 90° , indicating orthogonality of the lines. Within the vortex, the angle $\beta \neq 0$ (the velocity is non-uniform along the torus); (c) Distribution of vorticity after absorption $\omega^+ = F(\psi) \cdot r$ (with a "hump"); (d) Distribution of the "impurity" vorticity according to the generalized formula $\delta\omega = (F(\psi) - A) \cdot r$. The deformation of streamlines after absorption is clearly visible; in the equatorial region near the vortex boundary, a noticeable concentration of vorticity is observed.

8. Angular Momentum Before and After Absorption. The classical Hill vortex has no azimuthal velocity ($u_\theta^{(H)} = 0$), and therefore its angular momentum with respect to the axis of symmetry is zero:

$$L_z^{(H)} = \rho \iiint_V r u_\theta dV = 0, \quad (21)$$

After the absorption of a small vortex with transverse swirl of amplitude ε_θ , a nonzero azimuthal velocity appears inside the sphere:

$$u_\theta^{(\mu)}(r, z) = \varepsilon_\theta u \frac{r}{\sigma_\theta} \exp(q/2\sigma_\theta^2), \quad (22)$$

and the angular momentum after absorption is given by:

$$L_z^{(+)} = 2\pi\rho \iint_D r^2 u_\theta^{(\mu)}(r, z) drdz \approx 4\pi^2 \rho \varepsilon_\theta u (r_c^3 + 3r_c \sigma_\theta^2) \sigma_\theta. \quad (23)$$

Physical mechanism. The emergence of $L_z > 0$ signifies a qualitative change in the nature of the vortex: the Hill vortex transitions from a purely translational coherent structure to one possessing a weak intrinsic rotation. This is analogous to the Magnus effect: a body with transverse rotation undergoing translational motion experiences a lateral force - here, instead,

internal rotation of the fluid is generated. Since $L_z^{(+)} = 0$, the entire angular momentum after absorption is due to the captured vortex: $\Delta L_z = L_z^{(+)}$.

9. Moment of Inertia and Effective Angular Velocity. Treating the vortical region as a homogeneous sphere of density ρ and radius a , the moment of inertia with respect to the axis of symmetry is given by

$$J_z = \iiint_V \rho r^2 dV = 2M_H a^2/5 = 8\pi\rho a^5/15. \quad (24)$$

the moment of inertia does not change at leading order. The effective angular velocity characterizing the weak internal rotation is given by:

$$\Omega_{eff} = L_z/J_z \Rightarrow \Omega_{eff}^{(+)} = 15L_z^{(+)} / 8\pi\rho a^5. \quad (25)$$

Before absorption $\Omega_{eff} = 0$ (no intrinsic rotation). After absorption, $\Omega_{eff}^{(+)} \sim \varepsilon_\theta U/a$ which is small but nonzero. This rotation is not rigid-body in nature; rather, it reflects the net circulation of the fluid around the axis of symmetry within the vortex volume. The ratio $\Omega_{eff}^{(+)} a/U \sim \varepsilon_\theta$ confirms the non-destructive character of the process.

10. Transport and Redistribution of a Passive Scalar. The concentration of a passive impurity $C(x, t)$, associated with the captured vortex, evolves according to the advection equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial C/\partial t + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla C &= 0, \\ C(\mathbf{x}, 0) &= C_0 \exp(-q2\sigma^2). \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Why does the scalar redistribute along streamlines? In an ideal fluid, $\psi = \text{const}$ along particle trajectories, i.e. ψ is a Lagrangian invariant. Therefore, any impurity initially localized near (r_c, z_c) will be advected along the closed torus $\psi = \psi_H(r_c, z_c)$, spreading over it but not leaving this layer. After several revolutions, the impurity uniformly fills the torus (due to kinematic mixing; the flow becomes weakly non-integrable after absorption). The resulting distribution is **layered and step-like**: each closed streamline carries an almost constant concentration, while sharp gradients arise between layers. This constitutes **the mechanism of passive scalar redistribution**: in the absence of diffusion (Euler equations), there is no radial transport across streamlines, but reorganization occurs within each potential layer.

Integral measure of absorption completeness:

$$\eta(t) = \frac{1}{M_0} \iiint_{r^2+z^2 < a^2} C(\mathbf{x}, t) dV \text{ at } t \rightarrow \infty \quad (27)$$

The absorption time $\tau_{abs} \sim \tau$ is determined by the turnover time of the fluid within the Hill vortex. For the parameters used in the figures ($\sigma = 0.22a$, $\varepsilon = 0.18$), the impurity is effectively absorbed ($\eta < 0.05$) by the time $t \sim 4a/U$, which is consistent with Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Passive scalar transport in the Hill vortex after absorption. The impurity concentration $C(r, z, t)$ is shown at four time instants ($\varepsilon = 0.18$, $\sigma = 0.22a$, $r_c = 0.30a$, $z_c = 0.20a$). The initially localized cloud redistributes along closed toroidal streamlines, gradually filling the corresponding potential layer while retaining a spiral structure characteristic of the streamline topology.

Fig. 5. Comparison of analytical predictions (solid blue) with numerical results (red dashed) for the change in circulation $\delta\Gamma/(Ua)$ (left) and impulse $I_s/(2\pi\rho Ua^3)$ (right) as functions of ε . Parameters: $r_c = 0.35a$, $z_c = 0.25a$, $\sigma = 0.22a$. The agreement is better than 1-2% for $\varepsilon < 0.25$, confirming the applicability of the first-order analytical model in the non-destructive regime.

11. Numerical Verification. To validate the analytical model, we compare the predicted changes in circulation $\delta\Gamma/(Ua)$ and hydrodynamic impulse $I_s/(2\pi\rho Ua^3)$ with the results of numerical integration for $\varepsilon \in [0.05, 0.35]$. In the numerical calculations, the velocity field (equations 9–10) was integrated using a fourth-order Runge–Kutta method on a 600×600 grid in the meridional half-plane, while the integrals (19) and (12) were evaluated using quadrature methods. The comparison results are shown in Fig. 5.

The agreement between analytical and numerical results is excellent for $\varepsilon < 0.25$ (relative error $< 2\%$). For $\varepsilon > 0.3$, second-order corrections $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2)$ become significant; however, the qualitative behavior (linear scaling with ε) is preserved. This confirms the validity of the Gaussian perturbation model and the accuracy of the closed-form expressions (17), (19), and (23) in the non-destructive regime.

12. Conclusions.

Based on the analysis performed, the following conclusions can be drawn:

(1) **Preservation of structure.** In the non-destructive regime $\varepsilon \ll 1$ the Hill vortex retains its spherical shape and closed streamline topology after absorbing a counter-rotating vortex. The captured structure loses its individuality and is redistributed within the carrier vortex.

(2) **Core formation.** The absorbed vortex induces a vorticity perturbation $\delta\omega_\varphi$ (equation 17), which disrupts the linear profile Ar and creates a localized vortical core of width $\sim \sigma$. This effect is absent in all previous analytical studies of perturbations of the Hill vortex.

(3) **Vortex deceleration.** The propagation velocity decreases according to $\Delta U/U \approx I_s/I_H \sim \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$, which quantitatively describes the transfer of impulse from the captured counter-propagating vortex.

(4) **Angular momentum.** The absorption of a vortex with transverse swirl generates a previously absent angular momentum $L_z^{(+)} \sim \varepsilon_\theta \rho Ua^4$, transforming the Hill vortex from a purely translational into a weakly rotating coherent structure.

(5) **Passive scalar.** The impurity cloud reorganizes along closed potential layers (surfaces $\psi = \text{const}$), forming a stratified, step-like distribution that persists over timescales $t \sim a/U$ until complete mixing occurs. The spiral structure of the cloud is a kinematic signature of the toroidal topology of the streamlines.

(6) **Quantitative verification.** The analytical predictions for $\delta\Gamma$ and I_s agree with the results of numerical integration to within 1-2% for $\varepsilon < 0.25$, confirming the validity of the first-order model

The results obtained provide an explicit analytical framework for describing vortex absorption within the Euler equations. They are applicable to the study of interactions of coherent vortical structures in turbulent flows, to MHD dynamo models in conducting fluids, and to the theory of passive scalar transport in coherent vortices.

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